

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ABOUT OF MECHANISMS OF ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE IN PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA

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Abstract

The article analyzes data on the mechanisms of resistance of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* to various antibiotics. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* has been shown to be an opportunistic pathogen and a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in patients with cystic fibrosis and immunocompromised individuals. Due to their ability to easily adapt to the external environment, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains are often the cause of healthcare-associated infections. Antibiotic resistance in *P. aeruginosa* is multifactorial, as it can arise through innate, acquired, or adaptive mechanisms. New therapeutic approaches, such as quorum sensing, phage therapy, and the use of nanoparticles, may have significant antimicrobial effects against antibiotic-resistant strains of *P. aeruginosa* in vitro.

Keywords: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*; antibiotic resistance; opportunistic infections; resistance mechanisms.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a conditionally pathogenic microorganism and a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in patients with cystic fibrosis and immunocompromised individuals. Due to their ability to easily adapt to the external environment, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains are often the cause of healthcare-associated infections. Combating nosocomial is complicated by their resistance to disinfectants, antiseptics, and antibiotics. *P. aeruginosa* strains utilize their high level of innate and acquired resistance mechanisms against most of the drugs used. Furthermore, adaptive antibiotic resistance of *P. aeruginosa* has a mechanism that involves biofilm-mediated resistance and the formation of drug-resistant cells, and is also responsible for the persistence and recurrence of infections. The discovery and development of alternative therapeutic strategies that provide new avenues against *P. aeruginosa* infection are increasingly sought after and attract attention [1]. Various types of resistance mechanisms are observed in microbes, for example, natural resistance to certain antibacterial drugs in some microbes, genetic mutation, or resistance acquired from other species [2]. According to the World Health Organization, multidrug-resistant pathogens, called “superbugs,” are one of the major public health threats, causing several million deaths globally each year [3]. A critical group of multidrug-resistant bacteria include *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, and Enterobacteriaceae, which cause severe infections such as pneumonia and bloodstream infections in hospitalized patients [4].

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a gram-negative bacterium that can survive in a variety of conditions. The *P. aeruginosa* genome (5.5-7 Mb) is relatively large compared to other bacteria and encodes most of the regulatory enzymes important for the metabolism and transport of organic compounds. This pathogen most commonly causes lung infections that cannot be treated with antibiotics in immunocompromised people, and results in worsening lung function and death in patients with cystic fibrosis. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* accounts for more than 5% of infectious flare-ups in patients with

cystic fibrosis and is associated with increased mortality in these patients.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa has a high level of intrinsic resistance to most antibiotics due to limited outer membrane permeability, efflux systems that remove antibiotics from the cell, and the production of antibiotic-inactivating enzymes such as β -lactamases. Bacteria can acquire resistance to antibiotics through mutational changes or acquisition of genes through horizontal gene transfer [5,6]. In addition to high levels of intrinsic antibiotic resistance, acquired resistance greatly contributes to the development of multidrug-resistant strains, which makes it difficult to eradicate this microorganism and leads to more infections. Most antibiotics used to treat infections caused by *P. aeruginosa* must cross the cell membrane to reach intracellular targets. Antibiotics enter the bacterial cell in several ways: quinolones and β -lactams penetrate cell membranes through porin protein channels, while aminoglycosides and polymyxins interact with bacterial lipopolysaccharides on the outer membrane of gram-negative bacteria, facilitating their absorption. The permeability of the outer membrane of *P. aeruginosa* is extremely limited [1]. It is important to note that, in addition to being the main habitat of some opportunistic pathogens, natural ecosystems are also the places where all human bacteria, pathogens and commensals, along with the antibiotic resistance genes they carry, proliferate [7,8]. *P. aeruginosa* infections are often treated with aminoglycosides, especially tobramycin, as well as cephalosporins or β -lactam/ β -lactamase inhibitor combinations, such as piperacillin/tazobactam or ceftazidime/avibactam [9]. In addition, fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin), polymyxins, phosphomycin, aztreonam, and carbapenems are also antibiotics of choice, their use depending on the characteristics of the infection. However, the aforementioned intrinsic resistance of this pathogen to some antibiotics has prompted many to search for new β -lactam/ β -lactamase inhibitors such as imipenem/relebactam [10] or to develop new antimicrobial compounds such as plazomicin, murepavadin or doripenem [11]. It is also important to note that non-antibi-

otic therapies are being explored to counteract treatment failure when resistance to classic drugs develops. Among these strategies, anti-virulence compounds, efflux pump inhibitors, and permeable membrane compounds (administered in combination with antibiotics or alone) stand out as the most promising alternatives [12-14]. In addition, evolution-based approaches that exploit phenotypic convergence and negative hysteresis phenomena are currently being explored to combat *P. aeruginosa* and other human pathogenic infections [15-17]. Furthermore, the absence of OprF in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* leads to increased biofilm formation through increased synthesis of bis-(3'-5')-cyclic dimers (c-diGMP), an important messenger for the control of biofilm formation. *P. aeruginosa* possesses a number of specific porins: the carbohydrate-specific porin OprB, the basic amino acid-specific porin OprD, the phosphate-specific porin OprP, and the pyrophosphate-specific porin OprO. Among these porins, OprD is involved in antibiotic uptake. It contains binding sites for carbapenems, a class of β -lactam antibiotics, and the lack of OprD in *P. aeruginosa* increases resistance to this class of antibiotics. Bacterial efflux pumps play an important role in removing toxic compounds from the cell. In particular, proteins belonging to the RND (Resistance-Nodulation-Cell Division) efflux pump family play a key role in antibiotic resistance in *P. aeruginosa*. Therefore, the use of efflux pump inhibitors is emerging as a potential therapeutic strategy for the treatment of *P. aeruginosa* infections [17]. Like other Gram-negative bacteria, *P. aeruginosa* possesses an inducible ampC gene that encodes β -lactamase, a hydrolytic enzyme that causes the inactivation of β -lactam antibiotics. Resistance of *P. aeruginosa* to aminoglycosides is associated with multiple factors, such as decreased cell membrane permeability, increased efflux, ribosomal alterations, and enzyme modification. Among these mechanisms, enzymatic modification of aminoglycoside groups in the molecular structure of aminoglycosides plays a key role in resistance to this class of antibiotics [1].

In addition to modifications of resistance determinants, mutational resistance in *P. aeruginosa* is more multifaceted. Some examples of the multi-branched mutational resistance of this opportunistic pathogen are mutations in genes involved in the peptidoglycan recycling pathway, such as *mpl* or *dacB*, which increase β -lactamase activity [18]. Mutations can lead to reduced antibiotic uptake, modification of antibiotic targets, and overexpression of efflux pumps and antibiotic-inactivating enzymes, which allow bacteria to survive in the presence of antimicrobial molecules. For example, inactivation of the oxidative DNA repair system increases the frequency of mutations in *P. aeruginosa*, leading to increased production of β -lactamases and overexpression of the efflux pump. Antibiotic resistance genes can be carried on plasmids, transposons, integrons, and prophages, and bacteria can acquire these genes from the same or different bacterial species through horizontal gene transfer. The main mechanisms of horizontal gene transfer include transformation, transduction, and conjugation.

A biofilm is a collection of microorganisms that adhere to each other and are embedded in a self-formed

matrix of extracellular polymeric substances. Common mechanisms of resistance through biofilms that protect bacteria from the effects of antibiotics include prevention of antibiotic penetration, alteration of the microenvironment that causes slow growth of biofilm cells, induction of an adaptive stress response, and sustained cell differentiation. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* causes chronic infections in the lungs of patients with cystic fibrosis and forms biofilms on the surface of lung epithelial cells. One explanation for the increased antimicrobial resistance of *P. aeruginosa* growing in biofilms is that some parts of the biofilm contain cells with a slow-growing metabolic state, which constitute a subpopulation of resistant ones. Other reasons for increased transient resistance include more difficult diffusion of compounds due to the complex structure of the biofilm or the presence of elements that reduce the activity of antibiotics, such as glycerophosphorylated β -(1, 3)-glucans or cyclic- β -glucans [1].

Another major obstacle in the treatment of *P. aeruginosa* infections is the formation of bacterial persistent cells. Most planktonic cells can be killed by antibiotics; however, resistant ones are able to maintain viability and regenerate biofilms due to the presence of a quiescent state that inhibits the synthesis of antibiotic targets. Resistant cells do not multiply in the presence of antibiotics, but continue to grow after the antibiotics are removed. Furthermore, environmental stimuli such as nutrient deprivation increase the formation of resistant cells. Various conditions, combinations, and growth regimes that may occur during the infection process may temporarily increase the resistance of this opportunistic pathogen to several antimicrobial treatments, thus preventing the eradication of the infected bacterial population. Furthermore, studies have shown that the early appearance of tolerance mutations facilitates the evolution of antibiotic resistance, a feature of particular importance in the chronic course of *P. aeruginosa* infection [19].

Thus, antibiotic resistance of *P. aeruginosa* is a multifactorial trait, as it can arise through innate, acquired, or adaptive mechanisms. The diversity of antibiotic resistance mechanisms contributes to the development of multidrug-resistant strains, making them ineffective for the treatment of *P. aeruginosa* infections. New therapeutic approaches, such as phage therapy and the use of nanoparticles, have demonstrated significant antimicrobial effects against antibiotic-resistant *P. aeruginosa* strains in vitro and are therefore currently being considered as alternative or complementary therapies to antibiotic therapy.

References:

1. Yanovskaya D.I. Resistance of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* to antibiotics: formation mechanisms and possible alternative therapeutic strategies. | Actual problems of modern medicine and pharmacy 2022: Sat. material dokl. LXXVI Междунар. науч-практ. conf. students and young students, Minsk, April 20-21. 2022 g, p. 802-806
2. Catalano A, Iacopetta D, Ceramella J. Multi-drug resistance (MDR): a widespread phenomenon in pharmacological therapies. // *Molecules*, 2022,27(3), p.616.

3. Bloom D., Black S., Salisbury D., Rappuoli R. Antimicrobial resistance and the role of vaccines. //Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA., 2018,115(51); p.12868-12871
4. Billamboz M., Fatima Z., Hameed S., Jawhara S. Promising drug candidates and new strategies to combat the emerging superbug *Candida auris*. //Microorganisms, 2021,9(3), p. 634.
5. Tahmasebi H, Dehbashi S, Arabestani MR. Co-localization of *mcr-1* and β -lactamase genes in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* by high-resolution melting curve analysis (HRMA): molecular typing of superbug strains in bloodstream infections (BSIs) // Infect. Genet. Evol. 2020,85,p.104518.
6. Parmanik A., Das S., Kar B. Current Treatment Strategies Against Multidrug-Resistant Bacteria: A Review. // Curr. Microbiol., 2022, Nov 3,79(12), p.388.
7. Berendonk TU.; Manaia CM.; Merlin C. et al. Defining and tackling antibiotic resistance from a One Health and global health perspective. Nat. Rev. Microbiol. 2015 , 13 , 310–317.
8. Hernando-Amado S.; Koke T.M.; Baquero F.; Martinez, J.L. Defining and tackling antibiotic resistance from a One Health and global health perspective. Nat. Microbiol. 2019 , 4 , 1432–1442.
9. Bassetti M.; Vena, A.; Croxatto, A.; Righi, E.; Guery, B. How to manage *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* infections. Drugs Context 2018, 7, 212527.
10. Fraile-Ribot P., Zamorano L., Orellana R. et al. Activity of Imipenem-Relebactam against a Large Collection of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Clinical Isolates and Isogenic beta-Lactam-Resistant Mutants. // Antimicrob. Agents Chemother. 2020, 64, p.165-19.
11. Pang Z., Raudonis R., Glick R, Antibiotic resistance in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: Mechanisms and alternative therapeutic strategies. //Biotechnol. Adv. 2019, 37, p. 177–192.
12. Blanco P. Sanz-García F., Hernando-Amado S. The development of efflux pump inhibitors to treat Gram-negative infections. //Expert Opin. Drug Discov. 2018, 13, 919–931.
13. Imperi F., Fiscarelli E., Visaggio D. et al. Activity and Impact on Resistance Development of Two Antivirulence Fluoropyrimidine Drugs in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. //Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol., 2019, 9, p.49.
14. Ferrer-Espada, R., Sanchez-Gomez S., Pitts B. et al. Permeability enhancers sensitize beta-lactamase-expressing Enterobacteriaceae and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* to beta-lactamase inhibitors, thereby restoring their beta-lactam susceptibility. // Int. J. Antimicrob. Agents 2020, 56, 105986.
15. Roemhild R., Gokhale, C., Dirksen P. et al. Cellular hysteresis as a principle to maximize the efficacy of antibiotic therapy. //Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA 2018, 115, p.9767–9772.
16. Hernando-Amado S., Sanz-García F., Martínez, J.L. Rapid and robust evolution of collateral sensitivity in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* antibiotic-resistant mutants. //Sci. Adv. 2020, 6, p.5493.
17. Barbosa C., Mahrt N., Bunk J., Grasser M. The Genomic Basis of Rapid Adaptation to Antibiotic Combination Therapy in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. //Mol. Biol. Evol. 2021, 38, 449–464.
18. Levin-Reisman I., Brauner A., Ronin, I., Balaban N. Epistasis between antibiotic tolerance, persistence, and resistance mutations. // Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA 2019, 116, p.14734–14739.
19. Santi I., Manfredi P., Maffei E., Egli, A. et al. Evolution of Antibiotic Tolerance Shapes Resistance Development in Chronic *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* //Infections. Mbio ,2021, 12, p.03482-20.